
Staff Training, Participation and Job Autonomy as Correlates of Staff Productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated staff training, participation and job autonomy as correlates of staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria. This study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised of all 3,489 non-academic staff in the nine Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 50 non-academic staff each from the six purposively selected public colleges of education making 300 sampled respondents. Data collected through researchers' self-designed questionnaire titled 'Staff Training, Participation, Job Autonomy and Staff Productivity Questionnaire (STPJASPO) were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics (frequency count, simple percentage, mean and standard deviation) was used to analyse data based on research question while Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to analyse data based on hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results from the analysis revealed that the level of staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria was moderate. Also, staff training ($r = 0.200$, $p < 0.05$), staff participation ($r = 0.121$, $p < 0.05$) and job autonomy ($r = 0.299$, $p < 0.05$) had significant correlation with staff productivity. The study concluded that staff training, staff participation and job autonomy could significantly influence staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria. It was therefore recommended that the College Management should encourage staff to participate in the training programme, allow staff to participate in policy and decision making and give the opportunity to staff according to their potentials.

KEYWORDS: Staff training, Staff participation, Job autonomy, Staff productivity, Colleges of education

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INTRODUCTION

Staff members are the most important resources in an educational institution. Staff members are the main factors that must be developed to improve the quality of education in a school. Improving the quality of teaching and learning processes can be achieved through staff development (Iqbal, Sesmiarni, Harahap & Hadi, 2023). The staff members of higher education institutions are key resources in achieving the higher education set of goals. It is appropriate to argue that the success of every higher education institution significantly depends on the quality of its academic and non-academic staff. The motivation of higher education staff, who perform the role of teacher, researcher, and administrator is paramount as it largely determines the quality of the student's learning experience and the impact the higher education institutions make on society as a whole (Musa, Ahmed, Usman & Ibrahim, 2023).

Falola, Adeniji, Adeyeye, Igbinnoba and Atolagbe (2020) reported that to succeed and sustain performance in the highly competitive academic environment, higher education institutions need to ensure that the requisite competences of staff are developed and essential institutional support strategies that will enhance productivity are provided for the staff. Sheahan (2018) stated that productivity is the driving force behind an organisation's growth and profitability and organisational performance is a major multidimensional construct aimed at achieving results and has a strong link to strategic goals of an organisation. Ladipo, Alegebeleye, Soyemi and Ikonne (2022) defined productivity as a measure of efficiency of production which is usually expressed

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as the ratio of input to output used in the production process. When all outputs and inputs are included in the productivity measure it is called total productivity. Thus, staff productivity is the ratio of output produced by the staff.

Organizations invest huge amount on the human resource because the performance of human resource will ultimately increase the performance of the organisation. People invest in education in order to increase their stock of human capabilities which can be formed by combining instinctive abilities with investment in human beings. Examples of such investments include expenditure on education, on-the-job training, health, staff participation, staff promotion and job autonomy (Sheahan, 2018). To buttress the submission of Sheahan (2018), staff training, staff participation and job autonomy would be examined in relation to staff productivity

The success of any tertiary institution depends very much on the ability of the institution to train and develop its staff into a productive, competent and skilled workforce which is capable and willing to work towards the realisation of the institution's goals and objectives (Bappi, Bello & Jamari, 2024). Dagnev and Elantheraiyan (2023) perceived training as a means to update and upgrade employees' knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The scholars further stated that well-trained employees can achieve organisational goals, but without proper training, employees' maximum competencies remain underutilised. Quickonomics (2024) explained training as a process of improving individuals' talents, knowledge, and skills to perform a specific task. Training seeks to increase the output or productivity of an organisation's staff members by teaching them new techniques, modern technologies, and job-specific knowledge. In other words, training is an organised programme that helps employees learn new skills so that they are prepared to perform their jobs well. Egwurugwu and Onyeukwu (2023) asserted that tertiary education institutions must make sure that their staff members receive frequent training to satisfy themselves. Through this process, tertiary education institution workers acquire the necessary skills to effectively perform the tertiary education institutions' primary responsibilities, which include research, teaching and learning, and community service. Staff members who receive proper and effective training will have sufficient knowledge of the organisational structure, boosting their motivation to work, and overall performance. Additionally, they will be able to provide quality services, which will increase customer satisfaction and decrease complaints (Abimbola, Oyatoye & Oyenuga, 2020). Zindi (2024) affirmed that training programmes play a crucial role in enhancing the quality of education by equipping staff with the necessary skills, knowledge, and strategies to meet the diverse needs of students. Lack of training in educational institutions will result in low performance of staff as well as students.

Staff participation is the systematic practice of engaging staff in decision-making and problem-solving to enhance their commitment and contributions to organisational goals. Achieng, Susan and Atieno (2024) stated that staff participation practices have emerged as crucial factors in enabling organisational performance. Wilkinson, Dundon, Marchington and Ackers (2020) opined that staff participation and empowerment are key factors in fostering a motivated and productive workforce. They emphasised further that improved staff participation strengthens morale and assists staff in managing their workloads more efficiently, ensuring they have time available for their activities outside of working hours which leads to higher organisational performance. Williamson, Bayne, and Shay (2020) also observed that the participation of staff in decision-making processes allowed organisations to access a wide range of perspectives and knowledge leading to overall productivity improvement. Staff participation plays a key role in enhancing the effectiveness of staff productivity leading to overall organisational performance. Various studies have consistently demonstrated that the participation of staff in the decision-making process provides various favourable outcomes for organizations (Bieg & Toland, 2021). Achieng, Susan and Atieno (2024) investigated the influence of employee involvement practices on employee performance in public universities in Kenya. The study found that there was a significant positive correlation between employee involvement and employee performance with a strong regression coefficient. Employee involvement constructs accounted for 65.5% variation in employee performance. This means that when employee involvement practices are well managed, employee performance is likely to increase.

Job autonomy refers to the degree of freedom and independence staff members have in their work. It also encompasses the ability of staff to make decisions about how and when tasks are completed, as well as what methods to use. Smith, Pape, Ramirez and Pienkowski (2022) pointed out that the impacts of job autonomy on productive mindsets more than work flexibility. That is the future of work should enable employees to be productive, healthy and satisfied regardless of where they work. The contemporary nature of work necessitates people who are committed, engaged, flexible, and proactive. Job autonomy provides staff with full control over their tasks, and roles, choosing working approaches and enables them to make decisions that help employees feel highly satisfied as well as committed (Suárez-Albanchez, Jimenez-Estevéz, Blázquez-Resino, & Gutiérrez-Broncano, 2022). Nahrgang, Morgeson, and Hofmann in Elrayah, Moustafa, Hamid, and Ahmed (2023) stated that the lack of autonomy might affect the staff's physical health, mental health, behaviour, and performance. More job autonomy at work leads to reduce the probability of accidents, injuries, and conflicts. Job descriptions should be reviewed regularly to meet the essential needs of job autonomy. This practice should be done by organisations in all different situations because job autonomy helps staff and organisations to adapt to environmental changes. It can help staff members to lower their emotional exhaustion at work (Spagnoli & Molinaro, 2020). Elrayah, Moustafa, Hamid, and Ahmed (2023) investigated the impact of job autonomy on teachers' stress,

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satisfaction, and turnover intention among employees working in the education sector. The findings of their study revealed negative correlations between job autonomy and job stress. The findings also showed a positive correlation between job autonomy and job satisfaction and job stress and job satisfaction mediated the relationship between job autonomy and turnover intention directly. Zychová Fejfarová, and Jindrová (2024) investigated job autonomy as a driver of job satisfaction. The results of the study established the relationships between job autonomy categories and job satisfaction. Employees with a high degree of job autonomy feel in their jobs more satisfied than others. Understanding the relationship between job autonomy and satisfaction is vital for employers and policymakers to enhance job satisfaction, retain employees, and improve organizational performance.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The productivity of staff in Colleges of Education plays a pivotal role in achieving institutional goals, ensuring quality education delivery and promoting overall institutional development. In recent years, concerns have grown over the declining productivity levels among academic and non-academic staff in some Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Despite efforts at institutional reforms and various capacity-building programmes, some colleges of education still grapple with challenges related to inefficient performance, lack of motivation, and poor work outcomes. Several factors have been identified as potential contributors to this situation, among which staff training, participation in decision-making, and job autonomy stand out. Training equips staff with the necessary skills and knowledge to perform effectively; participation fosters a sense of belonging and commitment and job autonomy enhances innovation, initiative, and job satisfaction. However, in some Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria, these elements appear to be either inadequately implemented or poorly integrated into institutional practices. Inadequate empirical data linking staff training, participation, and job autonomy to productivity makes it difficult for administrators and policymakers to design evidence-based interventions that can improve staff performance. Hence, there is a critical need to investigate the extent to which these variables serve as correlates of staff productivity. This study, therefore, sought to address this gap by examining the staff training, participation, job autonomy as correlates of staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study was to investigate staff training, participation and job autonomy as correlates of staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. examine the level of staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria;
- ii. examine the correlation between staff training and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria;
- iii. investigate the correlation between staff participation and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria and
- iv. ascertain the correlation between job autonomy and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTION

This research question was raised and answered to guide the study

What is the level of staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

- H₀₁:** There is no significant correlation between staff training and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant correlation between staff participation and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant correlation between job autonomy and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised of all 3,489 non-academic staff in the nine Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria. The multistage sampling procedure was adopted in the selection of samples from both State and Federal Colleges of Education. In the first stage, stratified sampling technique was used to sample three States that have both Federal and State Colleges of Education out of six States from Southwestern Nigeria. The States were Ogun, Osun, and Oyo. In the second stage, a purposive sampling technique was used to select two Colleges from each of the selected States that is, one Federal and one State College of Education. In the third stage, simple random sampling technique was used to select 50 non-academic staff each from the six State and Federal Colleges of Education sampled in Southwestern Nigeria making 300 sampled respondents. Data used for the study were collected using the researchers' self-designed questionnaire titled

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‘Staff Training, Participation, Job Autonomy and Staff Productivity Questionnaire (STPJASPQ). The instrument had sections A and B. Section A contained the personal/demographic data of the respondents while section B contained structured statements to sample the opinion of staff on the influence of staff training, participation and job autonomy on staff productivity. The face and content validity of the instrument was ascertained by presenting the instrument to experts in the field of Educational Management. The thorough scrutinizing and checking of the instrument by the experts in the field of Educational Management ensured its clarity, relevance and un-ambiguity and thereby measured accurately what it was supposed to measure. The reliability of the instruments was ascertained through Cronbach’s alpha with reliability coefficient of 0.841.

RESULTS

Research Question: What is the level of staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics showing the level of Staff Productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria

Level of teacher productivity	Frequency (f)	% of Respondents	Mean level	Std. Deviation	Remark
High	142	47.3			
Moderate	153	51	42.01	5.810	Moderate
Low	5	1.7			
Total	300	100.0			

Table 1 showed the mean level of staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria. It was indicated that 142(47.3%) of the respondents had high level of productivity, 153(51%) of the respondents had moderate level of productivity, and 5(1.7%) of the respondents had low level of productivity. The overall mean score of 42.01 with standard deviation score of 5.810 obtained by respondents indicated that level of staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria was moderate.

H₀₁: There is no significant correlation between staff training and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria

Table 2: Correlation Table showing the Relationship between Staff training and Staff Productivity

		Staff Training	Staff Productivity
Staff Training	Pearson Correlation	1	.200
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	300	300
Staff Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.200	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	300	300

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field work 2025

The p value of .000 is significant at 0.05 level of significance with r value of .200 ($p < 0.05$). This showed a positive correlation between staff training and staff productivity. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The conclusion is that there is significant correlation between staff training and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant correlation between staff participation and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria.

Table 3: Correlation Table showing the Relationship between Staff Participation and Staff Productivity

		Staff Participation	Staff Productivity
Staff Participation	Pearson Correlation	1	.121
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.030
	N	300	300
Staff Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.121	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.030	
	N	300	300

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field work 2025

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The p value of .030 is significant at 0.05 level of significance with r value of .121 ($p < 0.05$). This showed a positive correlation between staff participation and staff productivity. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The conclusion is that there is significant correlation between staff participation and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant correlation between job autonomy and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria

Table 4: Correlation Table showing the Relationship between Staff Job Autonomy and Staff Productivity

		Job Autonomy	Staff Productivity
Job Autonomy	Pearson Correlation	1	.299
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	300	300
Staff Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.299	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	300	300

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field work 2025

The p value of 0.000 is significant at 0.05 level of significance with r value of .299 ($p < 0.05$). This showed a positive correlation between job autonomy and staff productivity. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The conclusion is that there is significant correlation between job autonomy and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result from the analysis of the research question indicated that 142(47.3%) of the respondents had high level of productivity, 153(51%) of the respondents had moderate level of productivity, and 5(1.7%) of the respondents had low level of productivity. The overall mean score of 42.01 with standard deviation score of 5.810 obtained by respondents indicated that level of staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria was moderate.

The result from hypothesis one with p value of .000 is significant at 0.05 level of significance with r value of .200 ($p < 0.05$). This showed a positive correlation between staff training and staff productivity. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The conclusion is that there is significant correlation between staff training and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria. The results revealed that training and development through job orientation training, conference attendance, workshop attendance, opportunity for further studies and periodic staff evaluation could enhance staff productivity. This result is in line with the finding of Zindi (2024) who affirmed that training programmes play a crucial role in enhancing the quality of education by equipping staff with the necessary skills, knowledge, and strategies to meet the diverse needs of students. Lack of training in educational institutions will result in low performance of educators as well as students. Additionally, Abimbola, Oyatoye and Oyenuga (2020) reported that staff members that are adequately trained will be able to provide quality services, which will increase customer satisfaction and decrease complaints.

The result from hypothesis two with p value of .030 is significant at 0.05 level of significance with r value of .121 ($p < 0.05$). This showed a positive correlation between staff participation and staff productivity. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The conclusion is that there is significant correlation between staff participation and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria. Majority of the respondents agreed that allowing staff to participate in policy and decision making and welcoming suggestion from staff regarding solutions to problems could enhance staff productivity. This result corroborated the submission of Aching, Susan and Atieno (2024) who found that there was a significant positive correlation between employee involvement and employee performance with a strong regression coefficient of ($\beta = .809, p < .000$). This means that when employee involvement practices are well managed, employee performance is likely to increase.

The result from hypothesis three with p value of 0.000 is significant at 0.05 level of significance with r value of .299 ($p < 0.05$). This showed a positive correlation between job autonomy and staff productivity. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The conclusion is that there is significant correlation between job autonomy and staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria. Majority of the staff agreed that allowing them to work according to their potentials, giving them free chance to do their job according to their capability and autonomy to useful information could improve their productivity. This result is in line with the report of Zychová Fejfarová, and Jindrová (2024) who established a

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significant relationship between job autonomy categories and job satisfaction. Employees with a high degree of job autonomy feel in their jobs more satisfied than others. Therefore, understanding the relationship between job autonomy and satisfaction is vital for employers and policymakers to enhance job satisfaction, retain employees, and improve organisational performance. Moreover, Nahrgang, Morgeson, and Hofmann in Elrayah, Moustafa, Hamid, and Ahmed (2023) stated that the lack of autonomy might affect the staff's physical health, mental health, behaviour, and performance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis of staff training, participation and job autonomy as correlates of staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria., it was concluded that the level of staff productivity was moderate and staff training, participation and job autonomy had significant influence on staff productivity in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result and conclusion, the following recommendations were made

1. The College Management should ensure regular job orientation training for both male and female staff and encourage them to participate in the conferences and workshop.
2. The College Management should allow staff to participate in policy and decision making and welcome suggestion from staff regarding solutions to the problems of the college as whole.
3. The College Management should allow staff to work according to their potentials and give them autonomy to useful information.

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